

CLASS PARTICIPATION AND PROFICIENCY IN ENGLISH SUBJECT: BASIS FOR ENGLISH CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT

Irene A. Sanchez^{1,3}

Cris S. Saranza^{2,3}

¹ Surigao del Norte National High School, Philippines

² Claver National High School, Philippines

³ Graduate School and Professional Studies, St. Paul University-Surigao, Philippines

Article history:	Abstract:
Received: August 6 th 2023 Accepted: September 4 th 2023 Published: October 6 th 2023	This study assessed the class participation and proficiency in English of 501 grade 7 students and 17 English teachers of Surigao del Norte, Philippines. Data were gathered from the survey questionnaire and were analyzed using mean and ordinal rank, t-test and Pearson-r, and Analysis of Variance for dependent samples. Results showed that grade 7 students are moderately participative in class undertakings by orally answering questions, performing group and board works, and role play, and are proficient in English in terms of reading, speaking, writing, and listening. It also showed a significant relationship between class participation and reading proficiency; however, no significant difference exists between the extent of class participation and the reading proficiency of the respondents.

Keywords: Class Participation; English Proficiency; Oral Recitation; Board work; Group work; Role play.

1. PROBLEM AND LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 Introduction

Students need to learn English to become professionally, academically, and socially competent. With the tough competition in the global workforce today, possessing a good command of English places a person far ahead of those linguistically non-fluent.

In the Philippines, it has been observed that many students, especially in remote schools, grapple incompetently using the language, resulting in a decline in the overall English proficiency of the country. Although the English language is deeply ingrained in the country's local culture, many youths still display a below-par English skill level, causing employers to refute them (Bulilan, R. S., & Ponte, S. J. T., 2018; De Vera, J. S., & De Vera, P. V., 2018; Hernandez, 2015). Furthermore, some students were observed to lack fluency in the language, as evidenced by their poor pronunciation, grammatically incorrect written compositions, and inability to express themselves in English adequately. This has alarmed the Department of Education to intensify efforts to provide an educational system that will improve students' English proficiency since the expected demand of most job-providing industries in and out of the country today are English-skilled individuals.

Increasing students' proficiency in the English language requires students to be constantly exposed to adequate and appropriate English learning materials and activities. Encouraging them to engage in group activities actively, role-plays and report presentations may increase their English fluency. These activities drive students to read lines, orally report in class, write scripts, and listen to their teachers' instructions and classmates' opinions. Thus, when students find their class activities fun, learning becomes spontaneous. In public schools like Surigao del Norte National High School, it has been noted that during the start of the semester, when teachers ask their pupils to give a short introduction of themselves in class, many of them screech in their seats out of extreme anxiety as they are unable to express themselves freely in the language they do not master. Furthermore, when teachers throw questions during reading exercises, many students become reluctant or give incorrect answers as they do not understand the question of their teachers or the article they have read. This has caused many students to remain passive in class, outnumbering those actively participating.

Based on the preceding discussions, the researcher was convinced to investigate the specific factors affecting the class participation and English proficiency of Grade 7 students of Surigao Norte National High School.

1.2 Literature Review

The concepts and studies included serve as support and basis for this research's development.

Class Participation

Participation in English class is anxiety-provoking for students (Alnahidh, F., & Altalhab, S., 2020); constantly engaging them in interactive activities wanes their hesitancy and low self-esteem in language use (Rincón, Á. A. R., 2023). Perkasa et al. (2022) stressed that due to the varying levels of English fluency in class, those minority students

feel that their words and ideas are unacceptable to their teachers and classmates, causing them to stay quiet in class to avoid ridicule.

Bekkering, E., & Ward, T. (2021) emphasized that class participation brings numerous advantages, mainly adding interest and engaging students. Monotony in class brought by teachers who constantly talk mainly bores students (Li, C., & Han, Y., 2022). With class participation, students hear another point of view and are encouraged to speak about their viewpoint. Class participation also provides teacher and student feedback (Tanis, C. J., 2020). When students talk, their teachers can assess the extent of their knowledge and the depth of understanding of the topic discussed.

Furthermore, when students are exposed to constant class participation activities, they come to class more prepared, reading ahead what was assigned the other day (Holdsworth et al., 2018). Class participation can even control students by catching their attention, especially when they are busy doing something, such as texting or chatting with a seatmate. It also enhances critical speaking skills and allows students to talk in the language of the discipline (Osborne et al., 2018).

However, despite the advantages of class participation toward academic performance, many schoolchildren remain hesitant to engage in class activities, especially during English classes. This can be attributed to the low proficiency level of students in English (Nilsson, M., 2019).

English Proficiency

Acquiring good English skills is a great avenue for academic and business advancements. Simply saying, if a person possesses a good command of English, he can easily understand and communicate with others, making education and business transactions easy (Clement, A., & Murugavel, T., 2018). Since most of today's school subjects and learning materials are translated into the English language, it is significant that students be taught and trained properly to gain proficiency in the said medium.

Many students in English classes hesitate to participate as they lack the facility of the language. Uchidiuno et al. (2018) expressed that when English is not the primary language, students automatically encounter barriers to participating in class as most subjects are in English. The lack of English proficiency causes students to take extra time to understand the lecture and formulate answers if the teacher calls to engage in the discussion (Nurjanah, R. L., 2018). Thus, students must master the technique, practice proactive conduct, and be involved in the discussion. Since this is not an easy transition, instructors must engage students in various fun learning activities and become sensitive to students' learning needs, especially when there is diversity in race, gender, and ethnicity in class (Leonard, J., 2018).

Possessing good English skills entails students being involved in activities promoting it. Class participation activities that aim to discover new material relevant in class, explore different perspectives, and invite students to relate relevant experiences are what teachers and students require. Employing activities promoting large group discussion, small group activities, and face-to-face interactions stir students' interest and motivation (Kumar et al., 2021). Students must read assignments, reflect on writings, and prepare for large group interaction (Hyland, K., 2019).

The following are the classroom activities that promote student participation to enhance their language skills:

Oral Recitation. This form of classroom activity enables students to speak in class as they are tasked to either read a passage in an article, repeat words as directed by their teachers, or answer questions as given (Moneva et al., 2020). According to Yang (2019), recitations reduce the negative transfer of the mother tongue, resulting in the development of students' speaking and writing abilities. Parallel to his point of view, Filipino and English stem from two different language families where sentence structures and discourse order are completely uncommon. This means that when students express ideas verbally or in writing, they first construct words in Filipino and translate them into English, frequently making their sentences grammatically wrong. Yang asserts that recitation increases students' language input, language sense is reinforced (Saragih et al., 2023), and memory power is strengthened (Anwar, M. A., 2019). That means, through oral recitation, students gain awareness of what words mean and how they should be pronounced, achieve a wider vocabulary and increased fluency in reading, and develop confidence in the subject.

Role Play. It is another form of classroom exercise wherein students are tasked with fictitious roles encompassing assigned lines to speak and behaviors that portray another character (Cano Mora, F. J., 2023). Engaging students in role-play enhances their reading and speaking ability because they must perform script lines that depict correct diction, pronunciation, and expression (Katemba, C. V., & Grace, R. M., 2023). Daif-Allah, A. S., & Al-Sultan, M. S. (2023) stressed that role play significantly creates interaction between teachers and students. As students interact constantly, they begin to develop fluency in English.

Furthermore, role-play expands students' vocabulary as they encounter new words and understand their meaning based on how they are portrayed in their behavior (Alshraideh, D. S., & Alahmadi, N. S., 2020). As a result, students develop a sense of mastery in words that they can apply to new situations. These exercises further harness students' listening skills as they need to be attentive to teachers' instructions and corrections (Daif-Allah, A. S., & Al-Sultan, M. S., 2023). In addition, watching movies in English and listening to English-spoken media at some point are role-play preparation activities that increase students' communicative skills (Najari, B., 2022). However, it has been observed that songs today contain numerous grammatical errors or because of the writer's choice to make the lyrics

poetic, and students tend to adopt the way native speakers deliver the language (Kumar, T., Akhter, S., Yunus, M. M., & Shamsy, A., 2022).

Board work. It is a form of activity in class that allows students to use the board to write out answers or to present a report presentation (Shukie et al., 2019). This exercise helps evaluate and increase students' language skills, specifically writing, speaking, and reading (Canagarajah, S., 2018). As students answer on board, their spelling and grammar are mainly assessed. More so, conducting reports in class increases their fluency in speaking and reading reports as they explain concepts and ideas. This also develops their comprehension skills on questions raised based on the preciseness of their answers (Mohammed, S. H., 2021). Students should be allowed to talk in a class by reporting or letting them explain answers to develop their language discourse (Sweet, M., & Michaelsen, L. K. (Eds.), 2023). By these, teachers can properly assess the extent of language learning on which they could base their teaching modifications.

Group work. It is another form of class activity where students work in small groups to accomplish a common goal: to accomplish given tasks (Elashhab, S., 2020). The group work largely enhances the four macro skills of the English language as students are privileged to listen to the opinions of other group members, write down their ideas, voice out their thoughts, and read assigned readings (Yang et al., 2022). According to Tursunovich, R. I. (2022), group work is among the most effective ways to conduct language activities, as students can freely express ideas with individuals of the same developmental age. Group work further enhances avenues for language practice and speech quality, creates individualized instruction, and promotes a good environment for student motivation (Toro et al., 2019).

Berry, S. (2019) found that among the effective means to increase class participation is to encourage teachers to break students into smaller groups, meet outside by groups, and use response cards. In these ways, students can share ideas, get involved in debates, and get feedback from the viewpoints of other students. Working together also allows them to gather more relevant information to share in class (Bovill, C., 2020). These imply that although receptive skills assist students in developing their language skills, teachers need to create better conditions to enact the learned skills productively.

Synthesis. The K to 12 Department of Education programs believe the country could produce highly competent graduates annually. However, the prevailing low English literacy among students in high schools has served as an impending threat to educational and economic success. To counteract this, schools must hone students' English skills by engaging them in effective classroom activities promoting active participation.

1.3 Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored on the concepts of Chance, P., & Furlong, E. (2022) and Howell, R. A. (2021) that active learning gives students greater involvement and helps students to become 'lifelong learners.' Interactive pedagogy, such as in-class participation, helps passive students turn into interactive ones who share ideas in the class and contend for their viewpoints. Since English is a foreign language and is still to be integrated into the language system of students, teaching must not only revolve around grammar and spelling but also enhance the interaction of students in class, which will harness their language skills.

Reflected in Figure 1 is the paradigm of the study. The first box contains the classroom activities that would help develop students' language skills: oral recitation, group work, board work, and role play. Allowing students to participate orally during classroom discussions helps develop language skills. Students usually encounter new words when reading books, and not unless taught how to articulate them properly, they will continuously mispronounce these words. Oral recitations help students develop good language discourse, making expressions and communication easy.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Study

Students are also encouraged to be involved in group work. Working in groups allows students to learn content and master the basics as they tend to discuss and share thoughts, thus deepening their understanding of the English subject. They also learn how the group functions productively by exhibiting support and contributing ideas to the group. Another area that students need to experience is using boardwork in class. This allows students to express individual or group answers on the board interactively. Lastly, students can participate in role-play activities, greatly enhancing their speaking skills. The second box of the diagram exhibits the respondents' English Proficiency level in terms of reading, writing, speaking, and listening. Proficiency in the English language compels students to learn and master the said skills, which can be helped by actively participating in classroom activities.

1.4 Statement of the Problem

The utmost purpose of this study was to determine the extent of class participation and level of English proficiency of selected Grade 7 students in the Surigao del Norte Division, Philippines.

Specifically, the study sought answers to the following problems:

- 1. To what extent do the students participate in English activities in the following areas?
1.1 Oral Recitation;
1.2 Group work;
1.3 Board Work; and,
1.4 Role Play?
2. At what level is students' English proficiency in the following areas?
2.1 Reading;
2.2 Writing;
2.3 Speaking; and,
2.4 Listening?
3. Is there a significant relationship between class participation and English proficiency?
4. Is there a significant difference between the respondent's extent of class participation and their proficiency levels?

1.5 Scope and Limitations of the Study

For a definite understanding of the entire content of the study, the following were presented for special consideration. This research mainly dealt with class participation and proficiency of Grade 7 students and English teachers in the regular class section of the selected public high schools of the said division.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Research Design

The primary research method used in this study was the descriptive research design, particularly employing the survey technique. This method was adopted as it aligns with determining the problems of class participation among the student-respondents. Specifically, the focus of this study was to help teachers understand why some students are participative and not participative in class.

2.2 Respondents

The study's respondents were English teachers and Grade 7 students of selected public national high schools of the division of Surigao del Norte. The researcher used the conventional method of getting the sample for students while the total population of teachers was employed. A total of 501 student-respondents and 17 teacher-respondents were taken as the subject of the study.

2.3 Research Instrument

This study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire, which is comprised of two (2) parts. Part 1 contained questions on the extent of students' participation in classroom activities such as oral recitations, group work, board work, and role-play activities. On the other hand, Part 2 contained questions on the student's proficiency in reading, writing, listening, and speaking in the English medium.

The following are the parameters used in the study:

Table with 5 columns: Scale, Parameters, Verbal Description (VD), Verbal Interpretation (VI), and Extent of Proficiency (Verbal Description (VD)). Rows correspond to scales 4, 3, 2, and 1.

2.4 Ethics and Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers initially sent letters of request to the school principal, asking permission to conduct the study. After the approval had been obtained, the researcher initiated the personal distribution of the survey questionnaires. After the questionnaires were answered, they were collated, tallied, tabulated, and analyzed with statistical tools.

Validity. Before distributing the research instrument to the identified respondents, the research instructors and experts checked the instrument's content. The comments raised were considered to improve and refine the quality of the questionnaire before administering it to the respondents.

Reliability. The run-rerun was administered to the 15 non-respondent students in 2 weeks. The data were analyzed, and its reliability results using Pearson r. The students' results on participation in oral recitation, group work, board work, and role play are similarly "reliable," with r results of .54, .52, .54, and .64, respectively. Likewise, the student's proficiency in English in reading, writing, and speaking obtained results of .76, .75, and .85,

respectively, and interpreted as "highly reliable" while listening is only "reliable"; hence, the overall findings revealed that the respondents consistently answered the test with understanding.

2.5 Data Analysis

Mean and Ordinal Rank. This tool was used to measure the extent of student's participation in English and their level of English Proficiency.

T-test and Pearson r. These tools analyzed the significant relationship between class participation and students' English proficiency in problem 3.

Analysis of variance by Dependent Samples. This tool was used to find if there is a significant difference between the extent of class participation and levels of proficiency of students in Problem 4.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Problem 1. The Extent of Participation in English

Presented in Tables 2 to 5 are the extent of participation of students in English as to oral presentation, group work, board work, and role play.

Table 2 centered on the extent of participation of the students through oral recitation. It shows average values of 2.96 and 2.86, representing the extent of participation of the students as perceived by them and their teachers, respectively. Both values indicate that the students often participate during classes through oral recitation.

All items concerning the oral recitation of the students are described as often done as perceived by both groups of respondents. The students obtained the highest mean value of 3.20 in item 1, "recite in the class when called individually," followed by 3.19 in item 2, "always ready/prepared during recitations," and they indicated the lowest mean value of 2.70 in item 4 "speak efficiently both in vernacular and English language." However, their teachers indicated the highest mean value of 2.94 in item 6, "express opinions related to the topics," followed by 2.88 in item 2, and got the lowest mean value of 2.65 in item 9, "make no unnecessary body/hand movements when speaking."

Table 2. Extent of Participation in English through Oral Recitation

Statement	Student			Teacher		
	Mean	Rank	VI	Mean	Rank	VI
1. Recite in the class when called individually.	3.20	1	Often	2.71	9	Often
2. Always ready/ prepared during recitations.	3.19	2	Often	2.88	2	Often
3. Volunteer during oral recitation and answer in English.	2.85	8	Often	2.71	8	Often
4. Speak efficiently both in the vernacular and English language.	2.70	10	Often	2.87	4	Often
5. Sometimes, ask relevant questions.	2.82	9	Often	2.82	5	Often
6. Express opinions related to the topics.	2.96	5	Often	2.94	1	Often
7. Show proper facial expressions when speaking.	3.06	3	Often	2.75	7	Often
8. Express well-organized ideas when answering.	3.01	4	Often	2.76	6	Often
9. Make no unnecessary body/hand movements when speaking.	2.88	7	Often	2.65	10	Often
10. Speak in a well-modulated voice.	2.93	6	Often	2.88	3	Often
Weighted Mean	2.96		Often	2.82		Often

Item 1, "recite in the class when called individually," has the highest mean value because, in the class, it is observed that the students study the topic ahead as announced by the teacher. During the class recitation, they find it easy to speak but with mixed language. The English language is not a practice at home, which the learners had to use in class participation activities.

Table 3 displays the extent of participation in English regarding group work. Average values of 3.17 and 2.94 are shown in the table, representing the students' participation in English through group work as perceived by the students and their teachers, respectively. Such values indicate that the students often participate in group work in an English class.

Table 3. The Extent of Participation in English in Group Work

Statement	Student			Teacher		
	Mean	Rank	VI	Mean	Rank	VI
1. Arrive at a collective decision in a group.	3.13	3	Often	2.82	7	Often
2. Exhibit leadership talents.	3.01	10	Often	2.99	2	Often
3. Participate in the group's sharing of ideas.	3.30	1	Often	3.00	1	Often
4. I am unusually more active when I am in a group.	3.04	8	Often	2.94	4	Often

5. Have varied opinions and lead to the group's actions.	3.02	9	Often	2.98	3	Often
6. Discuss, share, and evaluate our ideas.	3.07	6	Often	2.87	6	Often
7. Clearly understand the individual role in the group.	3.21	2	Often	2.88	5	Often
8. Encourage other members of the group to participate.	3.08	5	Often	2.76	10	Often
9. Exhibit good motivation skills to get ideas from members of the group.	3.09	4	Often	2.81	9	Often
10. Allow others to understand how to present their ideas clearly.	3.06	7	Often	2.82	8	Often
Weighted Mean	3.17		Often	2.94		Often

All items concerning the participation of the students in group work are described as often observed as perceived by both groups of respondents. The students obtained the highest mean value of 3.30 in item 3, "participate in the group sharing of ideas," which was also concurred by their teachers with the highest mean value of 3.00. The item with the lowest mean value for the students is item 2, "exhibit leadership talents," with a mean value of 3.01, while that of the teachers is item 8, "encourage other group members to participate," with a mean value of 2.76.

In class activities like group work, students are participative, as indicated in item 3, because learners find it enjoyable to do with their classmates. They love sharing ideas or brainstorming" within the group until they develop one idea. Group work encourages students to build leadership potential because one will always lead and push other members to participate. Through this activity, learners would be allowed to develop their proficiency capability.

Board work

Table 4 shows the students' extent of participation in board work. The average values of 2.98 and 2.88 represent the perceptions of the students and teachers, respectively, on the class participation of the former in board work. These values describe the students' participation in class by performing board work.

Table 4. The extent of Participation in English in Board Work

Statement	Student			Teacher		
	Mean	Rank	VD	Mean	Rank	VD
1. Deliver quality presentation.	3.00	5	Often	3.06	2	Often
2. Work in a convincing, appropriate, and correct manner.	3.06	3	Often	2.87	8	Often
3. I can establish credibility, resulting in creating a good impact.	2.99	6	Often	2.88	7	Often
4. I am capable of putting across ideas to the listeners.	3.03	4	Often	2.76	10	Often
5. Present board work in the English language.	2.85	10	Often	2.89	6	Often
6. Use necessary visual aids in presenting their ideas.	2.90	8	Often	3.05	3	Often
7. Observe the proper sequencing of events in the literary piece.	2.86	9	Often	3.07	1	Often
8. Possess a convincing style in presenting their works.	2.93	7	Often	2.76	9	Often
9. Entertain and answer questions from listeners.	3.07	2	Often	3.00	4	Often
10. Show seriousness and focus on the topic presented.	3.08	1	Often	2.94	5	Often
Average	2.98		Often	2.88		Often

The students got the highest mean value of 3.08 in item 10, "show seriousness and focus in the topic presented," and the lowest mean value of 2.85 in item 5, "present board work in the English language." On the other hand, the teachers obtained the highest mean value of 3.07 in item 7, "observe proper sequencing of events in the library," and obtained the lowest mean value of 2.76 in item 4, "capable of putting across ideas to the listeners."

The result implies that learners can present the topic seriously and with focus every time they have board work activity; it is because they were concerned about the highest point given to them by the teacher. Grades motivate students to do their best. Despite the difficulty of expressing themselves using English, students can still share their thoughts on the discussed topic.

Role play

Regarding participation in role play, the students got average values of 2.93 and 2.88 as perceived by them and their teachers, respectively, as shown in Table 5. These entail that the students often participate in role play.

Table 5 The Extent of Participation in English in Role Play

Statement	Student			Teacher		
	Mean	Rank	VI	Mean	Rank	VI
1. Exhibit self-confidence in the respective parts.	2.94	5	Often	3.12	1	Often
2. Show a good acting performance.	3.01	2	Often	2.88	5	Often
3. Participate and practice regularly.	2.94	4	Often	2.94	3	Often
4. Can relate well with the audience.	2.90	7	Often	2.93	4	Often

5. Can act with natural talent.	2.89	8	Often	2.76	7	Often
6. Present my part in a relaxed manner.	2.97	3	Often	3.00	2	Often
7. Show mastery of his/her lines in the play.	2.86	9	Often	2.71	8	Often
8. Exhibit a relaxed and natural acting on stage.	2.90	6	Often	2.71	9	Often
9. Never tried to upstage the other cast of the play.	2.80	10	Often	2.59	10	Often
10. Apply ad-lib when lines are forgotten but without being obvious.	3.02	1	Often	2.82	6	Often
Average	2.93		Often	2.88		Often

The students got the highest mean value of 3.02 in item 10, "apply ad-lib when lines are forgotten but without being obvious," while their teachers got the highest mean of 3.12 in item 1, "exhibit self-confidence in the respective parts." However, both respondents got the lowest mean values of 2.80 and 2.59, respectively, in item 9, "never tried to upstage the other cast of the play." All items, though, are described as often done by the students. Students often participate in role play for they lack self-confidence. In a role play like a stage play, learners find it easy to act because they were able to produce a movie presentation in their third quarter period. The requirement for students is to produce a short film wherein all of them are actors and actresses. Memorizing a script helped them perform well; however, on-the-spot activity made them hard to do.

Problem 2. Level of English Proficiency

The Level of English proficiency of the students in terms of reading, writing, speaking, and listening are shown in Table 6 t 9.

Reading

Table 6 shows that the students are moderately proficient in reading based on the average values of 2.95 and 2.82 obtained by the students and teachers, respectively. The students got the highest mean value of 3.03 in item 1, "read in voices which are bright, varied and expressive," and the lowest mean value of 2.85 in item 4, "read with vigor, expression, and clarity." Both items are described as moderately proficient. However, their teachers got the highest mean value of 3.06 in item 4 and the lowest mean value of 2.71 in item 2, "read with understanding, feelings, and expressions." All items concerning the students' reading proficiency describe them as moderately proficient.

Table 6. The Level of English Proficiency in terms of Reading

Statement	Student			Teacher		
	Mean	Rank	VD	Mean	Rank	VD
1. Read in voices that are bright, varied, and expressive.	3.03	1	Moderately Proficient	2.82	5	Moderately Proficient
2. Read with understanding, feelings, and expressions.	2.98	2	Moderately Proficient	2.71	6	Moderately Proficient
3. Usually appear alert and interested in topics read.	2.96	3	Moderately Proficient	2.88	4	Moderately Proficient
4. Read with vigor, expression, and clarity.	2.85	6	Moderately Proficient	3.06	1	Moderately Proficient
5. Exhibit varied rates and lifeless tone.	2.86	5	Moderately Proficient	2.93	3	Moderately Proficient
6. Show proper modulation and articulation of words.	2.94	4	Moderately Proficient	2.94	2	Moderately Proficient
Average	2.95		Moderately Proficient	2.82		Moderately Proficient

In the four macro-skills, reading shows that students are moderately proficient because reading alone is an easy task. The teacher gives reading materials to read as part of daily activities that might help them develop their vocabulary. Ten (10) minutes are allotted for reading activity alone daily. So, through this, student's reading comprehension is developed.

Writing

Table 7 shows the extent of English proficiency of the students in terms of writing. Average values of 2.98 and 2.82 are obtained, indicating that the students are moderately proficient in reading as perceived by them and their teachers, respectively.

Table 7. The Level of English Proficiency in terms of Writing

Statement	Student			Teacher		
	Mean	Rank	VD	Mean	Rank	VD
1. Organized ideas clearly.	2.93	5	Moderately Proficient	3.00	1	Moderately Proficient
2. Effectively write the story's beginning, middle, and end.	3.10	1	Moderately Proficient	2.94	2	Moderately Proficient
3. Show good vocabulary that correctly expresses the words' nuances.	2.97	4	Moderately Proficient	2.82	5	Moderately Proficient
4. Apply the rhetorical structure of the English language appropriately.	2.86	7	Moderately Proficient	2.93	3	Moderately Proficient
5. express closely related ideas.	2.91	6	Moderately Proficient	2.65	7	Moderately Proficient
6. Be able to satisfy the objectives of the exposition fully.	2.98	3	Moderately Proficient	2.88	4	Moderately Proficient
7. Be able to/ adapt a good and useful point of view.	3.05	2	Moderately Proficient	2.71	6	Moderately Proficient
Average	2.98		Moderately Proficient	2.82		Moderately Proficient

The students got the highest mean value of 3.10 in item 2, "effectively write the beginning, a middle, and an end of the story," but got the lowest mean value of 2.86 in item 4, "apply the rhetorical structure of the English language appropriately." On the other hand, their teachers got the highest mean value of 3.00 in item 1, "organized ideas clearly," and the lowest mean value of 2.65 in item 5, "express ideas which are closely related." All items are also described as moderately proficient.

The result implies that learners are proficient in writing because they are given ample time to think about what they want to write. Students told to write can gather ideas through vernacular and translate them later into English.

Speaking

The extent of speaking English proficiency of the students is shown in the next Table. Gleaned from the Table are average values of 2.93 and 2.71, representing the extent of speaking proficiency of the students as perceived by them and their teachers, respectively. Both respondents got the highest mean values of 3.04 and 2.88 in item 1, "speak with the right speed." They also got the lowest mean values of 2.86 and 2.71, respectively, in item 4, "can clarify or explain ideas." All these items are described as moderately proficient.

Table 8. The Level of English Proficiency in terms of Speaking

Statement	Student			Teacher		
	Mean	Rank	VD	Mean	Rank	VD
1. Speak at the right speed.	3.04	1	Moderately Proficient	2.88	1	Moderately Proficient
2. Relate clearly what is heard from the teacher.	2.98	2	Moderately Proficient	2.87	2	Moderately Proficient
3. easily catch the attention of the listeners.	2.96	3	Moderately Proficient	2.76	4	Moderately Proficient
4. Have the ability to clarify or explain ideas.	2.86	6	Moderately Proficient	2.71	6	Moderately Proficient
5. Share thoughts, feelings, and insights with clarity.	2.92	5	Moderately Proficient	2.75	5	Moderately Proficient
6. Initiate and sustain a clear, vibrant tonal quality without too much effort.	2.93	4	Moderately Proficient	2.82	3	Moderately Proficient
Average	2.93		Moderately Proficient	2.71		Moderately Proficient

To speak in class needs high self-esteem. The Table indicates that learners proved proficient in speaking because many of them can express themselves during class recitation. Speaking is different from writing, which is why, as a teacher, it is observed that learners find it enjoyable to know what words they should use to fit the vernacular they uttered. In addition, the class becomes lively because the use of mixed language sounds hilarious.

Listening

The listening English proficiency of the students is shown in Table 9, with average values of 2.98 and 2.94 from the students and teachers, respectively. These entail that the students are moderately proficient in reading English.

The students' highest mean value was 3.07 in item 1, "Listen because there is an intention to learn and to pass." On the other hand, their teachers said their highest mean value is 2.94 in item 2, "exhibit signs of cooperation by listening attentively." The students got the lowest mean value of 2.90 in item 3, "take mental notes of facts and important ideas," while the teachers indicated the lowest of 2.65 in item 7, "demonstrate skills in discriminating quality, pitch, loudness, and rate." All items obtained mean values, which described the students as moderately proficient.

The table shows the real picture of how attentive the students are because of their eagerness to learn and to pass the subject. Despite their difficulty expressing themselves in English, they could still express their thoughts in vernacular and English. Ahead of time, the teacher will announce what lesson will be discussed the next day for the students to get ready for it. During the discussion, learners are now prepared to participate, and the class will become livelier through the various ideas given in the form of recitation.

Table 9. The Level of English Proficiency in terms of Listening

Statement	Student			Teacher		
	Mean	Rank	VD	Mean	Rank	VD
1. Listen because there is the intention to learn and to pass.	3.07	1	Moderately Proficient	2.71	6	Moderately Proficient
2. Exhibit signs of cooperation by listening attentively.	2.98	2	Moderately Proficient	2.94	1	Moderately Proficient
3. Take mental notes of facts and important ideas.	2.90	7	Moderately Proficient	2.81	4	Moderately Proficient
4. Listen intently due to favorable communication and atmosphere.	2.96	3	Moderately Proficient	2.71	5	Moderately Proficient
5. Have listening habits that are relatively brief and easy.	2.95	4	Moderately Proficient	2.82	3	Moderately Proficient
6. Recognize slight differences in sounds.	2.94	5	Moderately Proficient	2.88	2	Moderately Proficient
7. Demonstrate skills in discriminating quality, pitch, loudness, and rate.	2.91	6	Moderately Proficient	2.65	7	Moderately Proficient
Average	2.98		Moderately Proficient	2.94		Moderately Proficient

Problem 3. Relationship Between Class Participation and English Proficiency

Table 10 displays the extent and significance of the relationship between class participation and English proficiency. The Table reflects t-values that are all greater than the critical t-value of 1.96 at 500 degrees of freedom. These values led to the rejection of the null hypotheses, indicating a significant relationship between the extent of class participation and the student's English proficiency as perceived by them.

Table 10. Relationship between Participation and English Proficiency as Perceived by the Students

Participation	Proficiency	r	t	Decision	Interpretation
Oral Recitation	Reading	.33	7.75	Rejected	Significant
	Writing	.31	7.27	Rejected	Significant
	Speaking	.25	5.88	Rejected	Significant
	Listening	.18	4.20	Rejected	Significant
Group work	Reading	.33	7.69	Rejected	Significant
	Writing	.27	6.20	Rejected	Significant
	Speaking	.25	5.67	Rejected	Significant
	Listening	.12	2.77	Rejected	Significant
Board Work	Reading	.42	10.38	Rejected	Significant
	Writing	.42	10.30	Rejected	Significant
	Speaking	.40	9.67	Rejected	Significant
	Listening	.27	6.29	Rejected	Significant
Role play	Reading	.44	10.85	Rejected	Significant
	Writing	.40	9.90	Rejected	Significant

Speaking	.40	9.73	Rejected	Significant
Listening	.32	7.65	Rejected	Significant

(df=500, t0.05=1.96)

A significant relationship existed between the extent of the student's class participation and English proficiency because learners can develop their high self-esteem in activities like board work, oral participation, and role play. Through activities, students find it interesting; they enjoy the activity and, at the same time, learn. In this way, the learners' English proficiency will be more developed. The more the students participate, the more their intelligence will be harnessed.

The positive r-values suggest that the more students participate in class, the better their English proficiency becomes. However, this may not necessarily be true in all factors based on the teachers' perceptions in Table 11.

Table 11. Relationship between Participation and English Proficiency as Perceived by the Teachers

Participation	Proficiency	r	t	Decision	Interpretation
Oral Recitation	Reading	0.83	5.79	Rejected	Significant
	Writing	0.38	1.60	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Speaking	0.35	1.47	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Listening	0.57	2.69	Rejected	Significant
Group works	Reading	0.39	1.63	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Writing	-0.03	0.12	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Speaking	0.14	0.53	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Listening	0.33	1.36	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Board work	Reading	0.52	2.37	Rejected	Significant
	Writing	-0.06	0.22	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Speaking	0.07	0.28	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Listening	0.30	1.21	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Role play	Reading	0.89	7.52	Rejected	Significant
	Writing	0.33	1.37	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Speaking	0.31	1.26	Not Rejected	Not Significant
	Listening	0.56	2.64	Rejected	Significant

(df=15, t0.05=2.13)

Only when oral recitation and reading as well as listening, board work and reading, and role play and reading as well as listening are paired, respectively, are the t-values greater than the critical t-value of 2.13 at 15 degrees of freedom. This rejected the null hypotheses, indicating a significant relationship between these paired variables.

Teachers can justify that students are average regarding class participation and English proficiency. Based on the result, it is true that learners are very good in the four macro-skills if they are used to the activities mentioned in the table. Because through the extent of class participation, skills, and capability will be developed. Students could establish self-confidence and practice speaking skills through daily oral recitation, group work, board work, and role play. When they gain high self-esteem, it is easier to express their opinions despite the number of observers.

Problem 4. The Differences in Class Participation and English Proficiency

Table 12 shows the difference in class participation and English proficiency among the factors.

Table 12. Difference between Participation and English Proficiency

Variable	df	F	F0.05	Decision	Interpretation
Students					
Participation	3 & 1503	1.93	2.61	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Proficiency	3 & 1503	1.64	2.61	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Teachers					
Participation	3 & 48	0.48	2.80	Not Rejected	Not Significant
Proficiency	3 & 48	1.07	2.80	Not Rejected	Not Significant

The obtained F-values are less than the critical F-value of 2.61 for students and 2.80 for teachers when students' class participation and proficiency are compared among the four factors. The null hypotheses are not rejected then, indicating weak evidence on the significance of difference. The result can be deduced from the fact that although learners are not that fluent in the use of the language, they still find ways and do their best to participate in the class, and in that way, they can gain self-confidence in expressing themselves orally.

4. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter summarizes the results of the study. Based on the study's findings, conclusions and recommendations are drawn.

4.1 Summary

The study aimed to determine the extent of class participation and English proficiency level of selected grade 7 students and English teachers in Surigao del Norte Division. It covers four class participation key areas: oral recitation, group and board works, and role play. Moreover, reading, writing, speaking, and listening comprised English proficiency.

A quantitative research approach was employed using a descriptive survey as the research design. There were 501 student participants and 17 English teacher participants in the selected public high schools, with 15 participants as part of the pre-testing activity. The data was gathered through a survey and then tallied and analyzed using frequency count and percent, weighed mean, t-test and Pearson-r, and ANOVA.

4.1.1 Summary of Findings

Based on the results, this study found that:

1. The student and teacher-respondents perceived that the students often participate in English class through oral recitation, group works, board works, and theatrical activities.
2. The student and teacher-respondents perceived that the students were proficient in English in reading, speaking, writing, and listening.
3. There is a significant relationship between class participation and reading proficiency.
4. There is no significant difference in the extent of class participation and reading proficiency of the respondents.

4.2 Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, these conclusions were drawn:

1. The Grade 7 students are moderately participative in class undertakings by orally answering questions in performing group, board, and theatrical activities.
2. They are moderately proficient in English as to reading, writing, speaking, and listening; they use vernacular more often.
3. Increased class participation leads to better English proficiency.
4. The students participate in four different tasks in comparable manners. Also, their English proficiency in four skills is comparably the same.

4.3 Recommendations

Based on the drawn conclusions from the study, these recommendations are offered:

School administrators should initiate an English curriculum focusing on activities promoting class participation. Activities such as oral recitation, group and board work, and role plays should be fun and motivating to drive student interest in actively participating in class. Moreover, teachers are encouraged to be vigilant enough in identifying students' language needs. Their activities should help students become competent in the language. They should continuously engage them in participative activities and intervene in those who are passive in class.

On the other hand, parents should serve as teachers' partners in monitoring and assisting their children academically. They must motivate them to participate at home through constant English interaction. They should also assist their children in their school work, which would help them prepare and become actively involved during the next day's class. Furthermore, students should come prepared and motivated in class. They should actively engage in oral recitations, group works, board works, role plays, and all other participative activities to familiarize themselves with and refine their language skills. They should grow confident in using the English medium, which is achievable only when they constantly use and practice it.

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